

Mental health literacy and work-life balance among university employees: The mediating roles of psychological well-being and psychological distress

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This study investigated the relationship between mental health literacy and work-life balance among university employees, examining the mediating roles of psychological well-being and psychological distress. Employing a convergent parallel mixed-methods design, quantitative data were collected from 202 teaching and non-teaching staff using the Mental Health Literacy Scale, Mental Health Inventory, Depression Anxiety Stress Scales (DASS-21), and Work-Life Balance Scale. Qualitative data were gathered through semi-structured interviews with a purposively selected subsample. Parallel mediation analysis revealed full mediation: although mental health literacy showed a significant total effect on work-life balance, its direct effect became non-significant when psychological well-being and psychological distress were included as mediators. Higher mental health literacy was associated with greater psychological well-being and lower psychological distress, both of which in turn predicted better work-life balance. Qualitative themes complemented these results by illustrating employees' experiences of workload overload, blurred boundaries, stigma-related barriers to help-seeking, and the value of coping strategies and relational support. Participants highlighted deficiencies in existing mental health initiatives, stressing the need for practical, skills-based programmes over informational materials alone. The integrated findings indicate that mental health literacy enhances work-life balance primarily by fostering positive psychological states and effective stress management. Strengthening employee well-being in higher education institutions therefore requires both individual-level interventions and organisational reforms, including skills-based workshops, improved counselling access, enhanced managerial support, and comprehensive workplace mental health programmes.

Keywords: employee well-being; higher education; mediation analysis; mental health literacy; work-life balance

Employee well-being and motivation are increasingly recognised as essential components of corporate sustainability. They play a significant role in enhancing organisational performance and employee satisfaction (Bhatt et al., 2024; Costa, 2024). In acknowledgment of this importance, organisations are prioritising well-being initiatives as strategic imperatives, underscoring their commitment to fostering a healthy workforce.

Employee mental health serves as a foundation for job performance, productivity, and organisational effectiveness. Good mental health is associated with higher levels of innovative behaviour and work engagement, which in turn lead to improved outcomes for both employees and employers (Lu et al., 2022). However, mental health is influenced by multiple factors, including demographic variables such as age, years of service, and place of assignment, as observed among frontline workers in the Philippines (Aduara et al., 2023). These dynamics highlight the complexity of mental health within specific occupational and cultural contexts.

In the Philippines, the Mental Health Act (Republic Act No. 11036) has established a comprehensive framework that promotes mental health awareness, provides accessible and culturally appropriate care, and mandates organisations to develop workplace mental health policies and programmes focused on prevention, identification, and management of issues (The LawPhil Project, 2018). The Act emphasises the role of tertiary institutions in cultivating a culture of mental health support and addresses stigma through legal protections that encourage dialogue and inclusive environments (Hilado, 2024; Feliza et al., 2025; Veralaw, 2018). Despite this legislative progress, challenges persist. Implementation in small and medium enterprises is often hindered by limited resources, while cultural stigma continues to discourage disclosure and help-seeking among Filipino workers (Dela Cruz & Fernandez, 2020; Santos & Ramirez, 2021). Prevalence of mental health disorders in the country has risen, with estimates indicating an average annual increase and millions affected (Alibudbud, 2023).

Mental health literacy, defined as the knowledge, attitudes, and beliefs regarding mental health conditions, symptoms, and available support, plays a pivotal role in recognition of issues, effective coping, and help-seeking behaviour. Studies among Filipino adults and university employees have reported moderate levels of mental health literacy, with socioeconomic status and educational attainment influencing knowledge of self-help strategies and illness recognition (Lampitoc et al., 2023; Rey et al., 2022). Workplace initiatives that embed well-being programmes, supported by strong leadership and employee participation, have been shown to enhance engagement and productivity (Juba, 2024).

Work-life balance further intersects with these factors. Imbalances arising from workload demands, blurred boundaries, and organisational stressors can exacerbate psychological distress and undermine well-being (Dey & Relajo-Howell, 2021). In higher education institutions, where employees face unique pressures from teaching, administrative duties, and service demands, the absence of well-established mental health programmes remains a critical gap (Calderón et al., 2021). Addressing this gap requires evidence-based insights into employees' mental health status and work-life dynamics to inform targeted interventions that comply with national legislation and promote sustainable organisational health.

The present study examined the relationship between mental health literacy and work-life balance among teaching and non-teaching employees in a private Philippine university, with psychological well-being and psychological distress as mediating variables. Utilising a convergent parallel mixed-methods design, the research assessed demographic profiles, levels of mental health literacy and concerns, work-life dynamics, and the interrelationships among these variables. Findings were

intended to serve as a foundation for proposing a comprehensive employee mental health programme tailored to the institutional context.

METHODS

This study employed a convergent parallel mixed methods design. Quantitative and qualitative data were collected concurrently, analysed separately, and then integrated during the interpretation phase to provide a comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon. This approach strengthens research findings by allowing convergence, complementarity, and expansion of results (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2018).

Participants

The study was conducted among teaching and non-teaching employees of a private higher education institution in the Philippines. Separated and inactive employees were excluded. The total population comprised 1392 employees. For the quantitative phase, stratified random sampling was used to ensure proportional representation across key subgroups, including age, department, and years of service. This technique enhanced the representativeness of the sample and reduced selection bias. For the qualitative phase, purposive sampling was employed to select information-rich participants who could provide in-depth insights into mental health literacy, psychological well-being, distress, and work-life balance experiences.

The recommended sample size for the quantitative phase, calculated using the Raosoft sample size calculator with a 5% margin of error and 95% confidence level, was 302. The final quantitative sample consisted of 202 participants. For the qualitative phase, a smaller purposive subsample was selected to allow for detailed semi-structured interviews.

Research Instruments

Four standardised instruments were used for the quantitative phase.

The Mental Health Literacy Scale (O'Connor & Casey, 2015) is a 35-item Likert-scale instrument that assesses knowledge and attitudes toward mental health conditions, symptoms, and help-seeking. Higher scores indicate greater mental health literacy. The scale has demonstrated good internal consistency (Cronbach's $\alpha = 0.873$) and test-retest reliability ($r = 0.797$).

The Mental Health Inventory (MHI-38; Veit & Ware, 1983) measures psychological well-being, psychological distress, and overall emotional functioning. A higher global mental health index reflects greater well-being and lower distress. The instrument reports excellent internal reliability (Cronbach's $\alpha = 0.94$ overall, with subscale alphas of 0.90 for psychological well-being and 0.90 for psychological distress).

The Depression, Anxiety, and Stress Scale (DASS-21) is a 21-item self-report measure with three 7-item subscales assessing symptoms of depression, anxiety, and stress over the past week. Respondents rate each item on a 4-point severity scale. The DASS-21 is widely used in research and clinical settings to evaluate psychological distress.

The Work-Life Balance Scale (Hayman, 2005) is a 15-item instrument that assesses three dimensions: work interference with personal life (WIPL), personal life interference with work (PLIW), and work/personal life enhancement (WPLE). It measures employees' perceptions of balance between professional and personal roles.

For the qualitative phase, semi-structured interviews were guided by the following open-ended questions:

Mental health literacy

1. How would you define mental health, and why do you think it is important for employees?
2. Can you share your thoughts on the current understanding of mental health among employees in the university?
3. How can you describe your current mental health state in relation to your work environment?

Mental health concerns

4. What common mental health issues do you observe among employees in the university and how do they manifest in daily life?
5. What barriers do you think employees face when it comes to accessing mental health services or support?
6. How familiar are you with the common mental health concerns and the mental health resources to address these concerns in the university?
7. Can you describe any experiences you or your peers have had in seeking help for mental health concerns?

Work-life balance

8. In your opinion, what does a healthy work-life balance look like for employees in the university?
9. How do you manage work and life demands?
10. What are the primary factors in the university that contribute to your overall well-being?

Programme development

11. What types of mental health programs or initiatives do you think would be most beneficial for employees in the university?
12. How can the university create a more supportive environment for mental health awareness and education?
13. How do you perceive the role of the university in supporting mental health in the workplace?

Ethical considerations

The study received approval from the university's Institutional Ethics Review Board and the Office of Research, Innovation, and Institutional Development. All participants provided informed consent after receiving full information about the study's purpose, procedures, potential risks and benefits, and their right to withdraw at any time without consequence. Participation was voluntary, with no coercion or undue influence. Confidentiality and anonymity were strictly maintained; identifying information was removed, and data were stored securely in password-protected systems accessible only to authorised researchers. Results were reported in aggregate form.

To minimise harm, screening procedures were implemented to identify participants experiencing significant psychological distress, with immediate referral to counselling services offered. Researchers received training in cultural sensitivity, particularly regarding Filipino attitudes toward

mental health and help-seeking. A debriefing session was provided to all participants at the conclusion of their involvement. Any adverse events were documented and addressed promptly in accordance with established protocols. There was no conflict of interest in the conduct of this research.

Data collection

Recruitment was conducted through email invitations and internal digital platforms. Quantitative data were collected via online Google Forms containing the four standardised instruments and an informed consent statement. Qualitative data were gathered concurrently through video or telephone semi-structured interviews, which were audio-recorded with participant consent.

Data analysis

Quantitative data were organised, cleaned, and analysed using SPSS and Jamovi. Parallel mediation analysis with bootstrapping (5,000 resamples) was performed to examine the direct and indirect effects of mental health literacy on work-life balance through psychological well-being and psychological distress.

Qualitative data underwent thematic analysis. Interview transcripts were coded inductively, with codes grouped into themes and subthemes to identify patterns in employees' experiences. Quantitative and qualitative findings were then integrated through joint display and narrative comparison to provide a holistic interpretation and inform the development of an evidence-based employee mental health programme.

RESULTS

Descriptive profile of participants

The sample comprised 202 employees drawn from multiple campuses, colleges, and departments within the institution. Ages ranged from 21–70 years, with a mean of 40.86 ($SD = 13.15$). The majority of respondents were female (65.2%), followed by male (32.1%). In terms of marital status, 54.8% were single, 37.6% married, 2.3% separated, and 2.7% widowed.

Most participants were based at the Manila campus (74.2%), with smaller proportions from Makati (16.3%) and Malolos (9.0%). Regarding tenure, 50% had been employed for five years or less, whereas 14.5% reported more than 30 years of service. Participants represented a range of academic and administrative units within the institution.

Parallel mediation analysis

A parallel mediation model was estimated to examine whether psychological well-being (PWB) and psychological distress (PD) mediated the relationship between mental health literacy (MHLS) and work-life balance index (WLBI). Indirect effects were tested using bootstrapping with 5,000 resamples.

Figure 1 presents the standardized path coefficients for the final model. The direct path from MHLS to WLBI was not statistically significant when mediators were included.

Figure 1
 Parallel mediation model of mental health literacy and work-life balance

Structural model results

The total effect of MHL on WBI was statistically significant ($\beta = 0.168, p = .015$). When PWB and PD were included as mediators, the direct effect of MHL on WBI was no longer significant ($\beta = 0.040, p = .467$).

The indirect effects were statistically significant. The indirect effect of MHL on WBI through PWB was positive ($\beta = 0.068, SE = 0.032, z = 2.11, p = .035, 95\% CI [0.007, 0.139]$). The indirect effect through PD was also significant ($\beta = 0.060, SE = 0.025, z = 2.417, p = .016, 95\% CI [0.021, 0.121]$). The total indirect effect was significant ($\beta = 0.128, SE = 0.042, z = 2.982, p = .003, 95\% CI [0.036, 0.209]$).

MHL significantly predicted PWB ($\beta = 0.158, p = .024$) and PD ($\beta = -0.211, p = .002$). In turn, PWB was a significant positive predictor of WBI ($\beta = 0.433, p < .001$), whereas PD was a significant negative predictor ($\beta = -0.284, p < .001$). The residual covariance between PWB and PD was negative and statistically significant ($\beta = -0.621, p < .001$).

Table 1 summarises the standardized direct, indirect, and total effects.

Table 1
 Standardised direct, indirect, and total effects of the parallel mediation model

Path / Effect	(β)	SE	z	p	95% CI	
					Lower	Upper
<i>Direct Effects</i>						
MHLS → WLBI	.040	0.055	0.727	.467	-.069	.148
<i>Indirect Effects</i>						
MHLS → PWB → WLBI	.068	0.032	2.11	.035	.007	.139
MHLS → PD → WLBI	.060	0.025	2.417	.016	.021	.010
<i>Total Indirect Effects</i>	.128	0.042	2.982	.003	.036	.209
<i>Total Effects</i>						
MHLS → WLBI	.168	0.043	2.982	.003	.036	.209

Qualitative findings

Qualitative data were analysed using thematic analysis. Four themes were identified: (1) negotiating work demands and well-being, (2) coping, support, and resilience pathways, (3) organizational culture and work environment, and (4) conceptions and awareness of mental health. Table 3 presents an overview of themes, subthemes, and illustrative extracts.

Across themes, participants consistently described mental health as embedded in everyday work experiences, shaped by both individual coping processes and structural workplace conditions.

Theme 1: Negotiating work demands and well-being

Participants described their work context as characterised by task overlap, competing demands, and time pressure. Workload congestion was frequently reported, with employees describing simultaneous responsibilities that required continuous adjustment of priorities. One participant explained that tasks often occurred at the same time, creating a sense of overload (“Tasks tend to overlap or become overloaded... sometimes everyone is working while inspections are happening at the same time” [“Nagsasabayan or overload yung mga tasks... minsan nagsasabayan”], P3).

Despite these demands, participants reported task completion as an expected norm, suggesting that work is maintained under pressure (“The work still gets done” [“Nagagawa naman ‘yung mga trabaho”], P11).

Disruptions to sleep and daily routines were commonly reported, with participants linking irregular sleep patterns to work-related demands (“My sleep is not consistent... sometimes I sleep at eight, sometimes at ten” [“Hindi siya consistent... eight or ten pm ako matutulog”], P8).

Participants also described physical and emotional manifestations of strain, including fatigue and emotional depletion (“You feel emotionally drained” [“Na-da-drain ka emotionally”], P17).

Theme 2: Coping, support, and resilience pathways

Participants reported a range of coping responses, grouped into individual strategies, relational support, and formal help-seeking.

Individual coping strategies included leisure and self-regulatory activities (“I just take time for myself... I listen to music” [“Nagme-me time lang ako... nakikinig ng music”], P2).

Relational support emerged as a key resource, particularly from partners and family members (“My partner has been a huge help in my life” [“Sobrang laking tulong talaga sa buhay ko ang ‘jowa’ ko”], P14).

Formal help-seeking behaviours were reported but less common. Some participants described accessing counselling services (“I had a chance to talk to a guidance counsellor” [“Nagkaroon ako ng time na makausap yung isang guidance counsellor”], P9).

Barriers to help-seeking included stigma and financial constraints. Gendered expectations were explicitly mentioned (“You are a man, you should be able to handle your mental health” [“Lalaki ka... hindi mo maayos mental health mo”], P6), alongside financial limitations (“If I had no money, I probably would not seek help” [“Kung wala akong pera, baka hindi ako magse-seek”], P12).

Some participants also described adaptive responses following distress, particularly during the pandemic (“I experienced depression and panic attacks... eventually, I opened up” [“Na-experience ko yung depression... eventually, I opened up”], P19).

Theme 3: Organisational culture and work environment

Participants identified several organisational factors associated with stress. These included interdepartmental challenges and procedural inefficiencies (“Sometimes you are challenged by people, even those from other departments” [“Nacha-challenge ka... kahit ibang department”], P5). Negative peer dynamics were also reported (“There is a lot of gossip and conflict... it feels like people lack independent judgment” [“Marami kasing siraan, tsismis...”], P16).

Participants described boundary erosion between work and personal life, particularly through after-hours communication (“Even on a day off, work still reaches you... you still receive messages” [“Day-off pero may messages pa rin”], P7).

Concerns about compensation and organisational practices were evident (“I want employees to receive their back pay on time” [“Gusto ko ma-receive on time yung back pay”], P13). Perceived lack of managerial support was also reported (“Before, it was 3 out of 10... it felt like there was no concern” [“Parang walang pakialam”], P10).

Mental health initiatives were described as primarily informational and limited in application (“We only have infographics, but what happens after that?” [“Puro infographics... anong gagawin pagkatapos?”], P4).

Theme 4: Conceptions and Awareness of Mental Health

Participants described mental health as central to daily functioning and work performance (“Mental health is important because daily work depends on having the right state of mind” [“Importante ang mental health... naka-base ang work sa mind”], P1).

Mental health was also conceptualised as dynamic and fluctuating, with reports of instability such as sleep disruption and persistent worry (“There are times when you cannot sleep or stop thinking” [“Hindi nakakatulog... laging may iniisip”], P15).

Participants expressed critical awareness of mental health terminology, questioning its accuracy and use (“It is easy to use these terms now, but are they used correctly?” [“Madaling sabihin ang terminologies... tama ba yung gamit?”], P18).

DISCUSSION

This study examined the relationship between mental health literacy (MHLS) and work-life balance (WLBI) among employees, with psychological well-being (PWB) and psychological distress (PD) functioning as mediating mechanisms. The findings provide a more precise account of how mental health literacy operates within workplace contexts, extending beyond direct effects to highlight the central role of psychological processes.

The quantitative results demonstrated that MHLS did not directly predict WLBI when mediators were included but instead operated through psychological well-being and psychological distress. This pattern indicates that the influence of mental health literacy is contingent upon its translation into internal psychological states rather than functioning as an independent predictor of behavioural or lifestyle outcomes. The presence of significant indirect pathways through both PWB and PD supports a model in which mental health literacy contributes to balance by enhancing positive functioning and reducing psychological strain.

This finding aligns with Lindert et al. (2023), who identified health literacy as a determinant of employee well-being that operates within broader organisational contexts. Their work suggests that literacy alone is insufficient unless supported by structures that enable its application, which is consistent with the absence of a direct effect observed in the present study. Similarly, Yang et al. (2024) demonstrated that mental health literacy influences help-seeking behaviour, perceived social support, and stigma reduction through indirect pathways. These mechanisms provide a plausible explanation for the observed mediation, as increased literacy may facilitate adaptive responses that subsequently influence well-being and distress. In addition, Zhang et al. (2023) reported that psychological resilience partially mediates the relationship between literacy and distress, reinforcing the position of PD as a key pathway through which literacy exerts its effects.

The qualitative findings further clarify how these mediating processes manifest in everyday workplace experiences. Participants described mental health as integral to their capacity to function effectively, with psychological distress associated with sleep disruption, emotional exhaustion, and reduced capacity to manage competing demands. These accounts correspond with the quantitative finding that higher levels of distress are associated with poorer work-life balance. The spillover of distress across domains, reflected in narratives of emotional depletion and disrupted routines, is consistent with evidence reported by Pradhan et al. (2024), who highlighted the impact of stress on performance and well-being in organisational settings.

At the same time, qualitative data identified pathways associated with psychological well-being, including relational support, coping strategies, and access to professional guidance. These accounts provide contextual grounding for the statistical association between PWB and improved work-life balance. The emphasis on interpersonal support and adaptive coping is consistent with findings from Yang et al. (2024), which highlight the role of social resources in mediating the effects of mental health literacy. Together, these results suggest that well-being is not merely an outcome of literacy, but a mechanism through which knowledge is translated into functional capacity.

The findings also draw attention to the role of organisational conditions in shaping psychological outcomes. Participants described workload congestion, overlapping responsibilities, and blurred boundaries between work and personal time as persistent features of their work environment. These conditions provide a contextual basis for the relationship between psychological distress and work-life imbalance. Abdou et al. (2024) similarly reported that work stress, role conflict, and boundary erosion are associated with increased distress and reduced balance, supporting the

interpretation that PD functions as a conduit through which structural pressures affect employee outcomes.

In addition to workload-related factors, participants highlighted procedural inefficiencies, delayed compensation, and negative peer dynamics as sources of strain. These organisational features appear to operate independently of individual-level resources, suggesting that employees may experience diminished returns from mental health literacy when structural barriers remain unaddressed. This interpretation is further supported by participants' accounts of existing mental health initiatives, which were described as predominantly informational and lacking practical application. The gap between awareness and implementation is consistent with findings by Zeng et al. (2023), who identified limitations in the effectiveness of literacy-based interventions when not accompanied by supportive systems.

Taken together, the results indicate that work-life balance emerges from the interaction between individual psychological processes and organisational conditions. Mental health literacy contributes to this process by shaping psychological well-being and distress, but its effects are moderated by the environment in which employees operate. This reflects a multi-level structure in which internal capacities and external demands jointly influence outcomes. On the individual level, coping strategies, relational support, and help-seeking behaviours are associated with improved well-being and reduced distress. On the organisational level, policies, communication practices, and resource allocation influence the extent to which employees can maintain balance.

This integrated perspective is consistent with broader literature on employee well-being, which emphasises the interplay between personal and contextual factors (Gómez et al., 2022; Juba, 2024; Lee et al., 2021). It also reflects the policy context outlined in the introduction, particularly the objectives of the Philippine Mental Health Act (RA 11036), which emphasises both access to services and the development of supportive workplace environments (Hilado, 2024; Ong et al., 2019; The LawPhil Project, 2018;). Within this framework, mental health literacy can be understood as one component of a broader system that requires alignment between individual knowledge, organisational practice, and policy implementation.

CONCLUSION

This study examined the relationship between mental health literacy (MHLS) and work-life balance (WLBI) among employees, with psychological well-being (PWB) and psychological distress (PD) identified as key mediating mechanisms. The findings indicate that mental health literacy does not exert a direct effect on work-life balance but operates through its influence on psychological functioning. Employees with higher levels of mental health literacy were more likely to report greater psychological well-being and lower psychological distress, which in turn were associated with more favourable work-life balance outcomes.

The integration of quantitative and qualitative evidence provides a coherent account of how these processes unfold within workplace contexts. While statistical results demonstrated indirect pathways linking mental health literacy to work-life balance, qualitative findings illustrated how these pathways are experienced in practice, particularly through patterns of stress, coping, relational support, and organisational conditions. Taken together, the findings position mental health literacy as an enabling factor whose effects depend on its translation into psychological resources and its interaction with the work environment.

Several limitations should be considered when interpreting these findings. The cross-sectional design restricts causal inference, as relationships between variables are based on a single time point. Although mediation analysis provides insight into potential mechanisms, longitudinal or experimental designs would be required to establish temporal ordering. The qualitative component, while providing depth, may not capture the full range of experiences across all departments or campuses, particularly given variations in organisational culture. In addition, the reliance on self-report measures introduces the possibility of response bias, particularly in relation to sensitive topics such as mental health and distress.

Future research may extend these findings by examining additional mediating or moderating variables, including leadership styles, job demands, or organisational support structures. Longitudinal approaches would allow for the examination of changes in mental health literacy and psychological outcomes over time, while comparative studies across institutions could clarify the role of contextual variation. Further exploration of how mental health literacy is operationalised within workplace interventions may also provide insight into how knowledge can be more effectively translated into practice.

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